

Student and staff perceptions of fairness in assessment and feedback practices

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Abstract

“Blind marking” is said to reduce the chance of bias arising in the assessment of written assignments. Several major universities have adopted the practise in an effort to improve fairness. However it’s unknown whether this has the support of students and staff at Deakin. In this enquiry, I have undertaken a small scale survey of students and teaching staff in the School of Life and Environmental Sciences to gauge the perceived fairness of assessment practices currently as well as the support for switching to blind marking of written assessments. Student and staff respondents agreed that blind marking would improve assessment fairness and indicated support for a change in assessment practises toward blind marking. Given the small scale nature of this study, a larger survey of student and staff across faculties is warranted.

Introduction

Blind marking is a process where the assessor does not know the identity of the student whose work is under examination. Blind marking has been proposed to be a safeguard against conscious and unconscious bias in student assessment. Dozens of studies into the efficacy of blind marking have been undertaken at different educational levels. In these studies, the presence of bias is determined by comparing the grades of student work that is marked blind and unblind. A meta-analysis of 20 blind marking studies found that there is a statistically significant bias against certain student groups including women and ethnic minorities (Malouff & Thorsteinsson 2016). Another study found overall only a small degree of bias due to unblinded marking, but that the degree of bias was larger for written assignments as opposed to examinations (Hinton & Higson 2017). Given the share of grades given to examinations is shrinking over time in favour of assignments and coursework (Richardson 2014), the problem of bias is likely to become greater over time.

Already, Deakin and most major Australian Universities have a semi-blind policy regarding examinations (Deakin University 2018; The University of Melbourne 2018). A number of Universities have also implemented blind marking procedures for written assignments. For example the Moodle learning management system (LMS) used by University of New England streamlines the process of blind marking by managing the blinding and unblinding process electronically, overcoming the problems of additional workload, chance of mistakes, and the requirement for a second person to do the blinding (UNE 2019). According to the University of Melbourne Policy, anonymous marking is recommended whenever practicable (The University of Melbourne 2018), however the rollout has encountered technical problems (The University of Melbourne 2019). The LMS provider used by Deakin, called D2L, is beginning to offer blind marking features (Paul, 2017), so there is a possibility that it may be implemented in coming years at Deakin.

While research suggests that there is some bias reducing benefit to blind marking, it is important to gauge students' perceptions of the current levels of fairness in assessment and feedback and whether a transition to blind marking would improve the perceived fairness of this process. Indeed a survey by the UK National Union of Students indicated that over 40% of students believed that discrimination and bias influenced their assessment and feedback, which prompted NUS to initiate a program to increase student awareness and advocacy of blind marking (NUS, 2008). Although overseas studies suggest that blind marking has student support, there is scarce information on whether this is also the case in Australia. This project will address whether blind marking has the support of students at Deakin; and if respondent numbers enable it, determine whether blind marking is perceived to be fairer by student groups that have been reported to have been discriminated against previously, namely women and people with non-European backgrounds. As blind marking represents a major shift in work behaviours for

teaching staff, another goal of this project will be to gauge staff attitudes to blind marking and appetite for change.

Methods

Staff survey: Eighty Deakin School of Life and Environmental Sciences (LES) teaching staff including lecturers, demonstrators and teaching assistants were asked by email to complete a 15-question survey via Qualtrics. **Student survey:** Up to 197 students 2nd and 3rd year LES students were invited to take part in the survey by the unit chair posting a news item to the unit site. **Ethics:** In order to meet ethical guidelines, survey participation was voluntary and responses were anonymous. The study was approved by the Head of School (LES) and SEBE Ethical Review Board prior to data collection (Ref: STEC-50-2019-ZIEMANN). A copy of the survey questions and responses is included in the appendix. **Statistics:** No statistical tests were performed. Histograms shown in the appendix were generated either by Qualtrix or in R (R Core Team 2019).

Results and discussion

Students and staff were asked to complete a survey about their opinions on assessment fairness and blind marking. It is important to know the demographic make-up of the student and staff groups, as certain student and staff groups may have different perceptions of assessment bias. This general demographic information is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 - Demographic information of respondents. Mean and standard deviation values are given.

	Student survey	Teaching staff survey
No. responses	23	15
Trimesters completed in past 5 yrs	6.06 ± 1.61	8.93 ± 3.84
Female / Male / Not disclosed	15 / 7 / 1	6 / 9 / 0
European ethnicity / non European	18 / 5	12 / 3

The collated responses to the student survey are given in Table 2. The collated responses to the teaching staff survey are given in Table 3. Full details of responses are found in the appendix.

Table 2 - student survey responses.

Question	Response	Min	Max	Median	Mean	Std Dev
4 - Do you think you receive sufficient feedback on your written assignments?	Strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (7)	1	7	6	5.57	1.38
5- Do you believe your assignment marks have been influenced by conscious bias of teaching staff?	Strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (7)	1	7	2	2.74	1.72
6 - Do you believe your assignment marks have been influenced by unconscious bias of teaching staff?	Strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (7)	1	7	3	3.45	1.83
7 - Have you heard of the terms "blind marking" or "anonymous marking" before?	Yes or no	Yes = 14 No = 8 Not answered = 1				
8 - In your opinion, what proportion (percent, %) of teaching staff are biased in their marking?	Slider from 0% to 100%	0	100	15	23.32	27.64
9 - Blind marking is a procedure where the assessor does not know the identity of the student whose work is under assessment. Do you think blind marking would improve the fairness of grading written assignments?	Strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (7)	4	7	6	5.86	1.01
Q10 - Do you think Deakin should implement blind marking procedures for written assignments?	Strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (7)	4	7	5.5	5.50	1.08

Table 3 - Staff survey responses.

Question	Response	Min	Max	Median	Mean	Std Dev
4 - Approximately how much time would you spend marking assignments each trimester?	Categories: None, 1-40 hrs, 41-80 hrs, >80 hrs	None = 0 1-40 hrs = 5 41-80 hrs = 10 >80 hrs = 0				
5 - For the units you teach on average, what percentage of grades are given to written assignments such as essays and reports? Use the slider to specify.	Slider from 0% to 100%	20	92	40	48.93	19.57
6 - What proportion of your marking is done alone, or part of a marking team?	% done alone	40	100	80	77.76	18.87
7 - Have you heard of the terms "blind marking" or "anonymous marking" before?	Yes or no	Yes = 13 No = 2				
8 - Do you think some teaching staff engage in conscious bias when marking student assignments?	Strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (7)	2	7	4	4.40	1.50
9 - Do you think some teaching staff have an unconscious bias when marking student assignments?	Strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (7)	3	7	5	5.07	1.24
10 - In your opinion, what proportion (%) of teaching staff are biased in their marking? Use the slider to specify	Slider from 0% to 100%	0	100	30	41.67	35.35
11 - Blind marking is a procedure where the assessor does not know the identity of the student whose work is under assessment. Do you think blind marking would improve the fairness of grading written assignments?	Strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (7)	4	7	6	5.73	1.00
12 - Have you already implemented some type of blind marking of assignments at Deakin (not including exams)?	Categories: None, Some, Most, All	None = 7 Some = 4 Most = 1 All = 3				
13 - If it required no extra work from you or your teaching team, would you support Deakin implementing blind marking for written assignments?	Strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (7)	3	7	6	5.87	1.31

From the results we can make the following observations. Student respondents were generally happy with the level of feedback received on their written assignments. Student respondents generally believe that their grades have not been influenced by conscious bias but when asked about unconscious bias the responses were mixed. This reflects the good standing with which students perceive staff integrity. Consistent with this, when asked about what proportion of teaching staff are biased in their marking, student respondents reported a median of 15%. In contrast, teaching staff respondents reported a median of 30%. When it came to whether students knew about blind marking, 37% had not heard about it before, so perhaps there is scope to engage students in a dialogue to build greater awareness among students as to the biases in assessment. As expected, awareness of blind marking among teaching staff respondents was high (87%).

It was surprising to see that the large majority of marking was done by single teaching staff working solo as opposed to marking teams. It is in this environment that there is a risk that students grades can be affected by bias with little chance of it being detected by fellow teaching team members. Perhaps there should be guidelines in place to encourage more marking be done in teams as this has the potential to better ensure assessment consistency across units in the school (Price 2005).

In general, student and staff respondents agreed to a similar extent that blind marking would improve the fairness of written assessments. Similarly, both students and staff were in favour of implementing blind marking. Although student respondents perceived most staff to grade student work impartially and fairly, their responses here suggest that there is room to improve assessment practices by implementing blind marking for written assignments. The support from staff came with the condition that blind marking did not impose any extra work on the teaching team, as implied in staff survey question 13. As teaching staff experience fluctuations of workload throughout a trimester, they are particularly sensitive to any extra workload that occurs at the same time as marking. As most markers do this work solo, this translates into either extra overtime during these busy periods, delays to student feedback or poorer feedback quality.

Although it is not compulsory within the school, nor facilitated by the current LMS (D2L), about half of the teaching staff respondents have already implemented some type of blind marking procedure, which is a higher rate of adoption than I had expected. Because staff interest in blind marking was so high, I composed a free web-service called Blinder to automate batch document blinding (Ziemann 2019). The webpage service is found at (www.blinder.cc) and is in experimental-phase testing. Once more comprehensive testing is completed, I will publicize the tool to the broader education community. It is possible that in future, D2L will provide its own blind marking features.

A limitation of this enquiry is that it is a small-scale survey of students and staff within the LES and might not be representative of opinions in other schools and faculties. Despite this limitation it was quite clear that respondents generally were supportive of blind marking. I had originally set out to determine whether certain gender and ethnicity groups perceive assessment bias differently, however there were too few

responses to make any robust subgroup observations. This warrants an expanded survey to determine if support for blind marking exists in faculties and schools beyond LES and also within gender and ethnic subgroups. Results of this survey will be shared with the Deakin University Student Association Student Council with a view to initiating an expanded survey of Association members' views.

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Appendix

Student survey responses

Question 4 - Do you think you receive sufficient feedback on your written assignments?

Question 5 - Do you believe your assignment marks have been influenced by conscious bias of teaching staff?

Q6 - Do you believe your assignment marks have been influenced by unconscious bias of teaching staff?

Question 7 - Have you heard of the terms “blind marking” or “anonymous marking” before?

Question 8 - In your opinion, what proportion (percent, %) of teaching staff are biased in their marking?

Question 9 - Blind marking is a procedure where the assessor does not know the identity of the student whose work is under assessment. Do you think blind marking would improve the fairness of grading written assignments?

Question 10 - Do you think Deakin should implement blind marking procedures for written assignments?

Question 11 - Do you have any further comments you would like to share about assessment bias or blind marking? Please provide below.

Responses to question 11 are provided below unedited.

I have had positive experiences in the SLES marking.

blind marking would be a good way to eliminate bias however some if the teacher knows a student is struggling with the work they can mark it accordingly if they know who's paper is who's.

The only way that I see have a completely unbiased and blinded assessment for assignments/exams (in my view) is to have the Deakin University lecturer deliver the on-campus teaching. As well as having a third and/or fourth party, familiar with the course work to Assess the written assessment(s) depending upon the number of assessments etc... The course would then require a fifth and/or sixth independent assessor to write the tests/exams (understanding that there needs to be an alternative test/exam); So that's 8 assessors so far. However, this would then have to have an independent assessor to review all marks at the end of trimester. To make it a completely blind assessment the assessor cannot know which assessment question/exam is being given to each student, and the student cannot identify her/himself on the assessment by any means (including student number). This makes it impossible to assign individual marks to students, unless the task is 'un-blinded', which seems impossible in this given scenario. So to sum up, it seems impossible to have unbiased and blind assessment of student work and still assign students an individual mark.

It takes far too long to get feedback from assignments, and the feedback is usually of very low constructive value. It is clear to me that under the current system some very low value people in positions of unit chair give students poor marks due to difference in opinion, but high enough that the student has absolutely no recourse through university channels. Perhaps blind marking would mitigate this but I would rather the university remove the problem individuals very publicly and add a "no dickhead behaviour" clause to all positions within the university in the interests of divertisy and inclusion.

Staff survey responses

Question 4 - Approximately how much time would you spend marking assignments each trimester?

Question 5 - For the units you teach on average, what percentage of grades are given to written assignments such as essays and reports? Use the slider to specify.

Question 6 - What proportion of your marking is done alone, or part of a marking team?

Question 7 - Have you heard of the terms “blind marking” or “anonymous marking” before?

Question 8 - Do you think some teaching staff engage in conscious bias when marking student assignments?

Question 9 - Do you think some teaching staff have an unconscious bias when marking student assignments?

Question 10 - In your opinion, what proportion (%) of teaching staff are biased in their marking? Use the slider to specify

Question 11 - Blind marking is a procedure where the assessor does not know the identity of the student whose work is under assessment. Do you think blind marking would improve the fairness of grading written assignments?

Question 12 - Have you already implemented some type of blind marking of assignments at Deakin (not including exams)?

Question 13 - If it required no extra work from you or your teaching team, would you support Deakin implementing blind marking for written assignments?

Question 14 - Do you have any further comments you would like to share about assessment bias or blind marking?

I think it is incumbent on all staff to complete blind marking where applicable
Research has shown that even an awareness of bias does not enable you to overcome biases in your work (whether that is in the education sector or elsewhere). So while education about the issue is worthwhile, there must be other methods implemented to guarantee assignments are marked fairly.
Students who have struggled with the material, those on LAPs, and those with special consideration will be severely disadvantaged.
The better we get to know our students, the more we are likely to be biased when marking them.